

PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION AND SURFACE QUALITY DURING FORMING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES WITH A COLLECTION OF RUBBER PARTICLES AS MOULD HALF

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SUMMARY

Pressing thermoplastic composites with a collection of rubber particles as one mould half offers considerable advantages over conventional pressing with a solid rubber mould half. The present paper shows the influence of both rubber hardness and particles' shape and dimensions on the pressure distribution during pressure forming. Results show that the hardness of the rubber influences the uniformity of the pressure distribution, while the shape of the particles allows for a better surface quality. Preliminary production shows good agreement with tests results.

Keywords: Rubber Forming, Thermoplastic Composites, Surface Quality, Pressure Distribution

INTRODUCTION

Rubber pressure forming of thermoplastic composites is a fabrication process that allows the series production of composite parts with high mechanical properties. A typical rubber forming set-up consists of a rigid mould, a flexible (rubber) mould and a clamping or sliding frame (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Principle of rubber forming

When the thermoplastic laminate is at the necessary processing temperature, the material is quickly transferred to the forming press by a clamping frame, which transfers the hot laminate to the forming system.

When the hot laminate is positioned between the two moulds the press is closed and the product is formed. With this production method, the typical forming time is a few seconds. When the shape is formed and final consolidation is assured, the product must be cooled down under pressure. After cooling down, the product can be taken out of the mould.

The limited implementation of this process in industry is due to the lack of proper design and process tools. In particular the large amount of time spent in the definition of the suitable rubber mould, normally made based on the craftsmanship of the manufacturing engineer and material supplier, leads to the decision of producing very simple parts, mainly flat plates or single curved panels to avoid long development periods. The design difficulties with rubber pressing originate from various physical effects that are briefly explained below.

A characteristic of the silicon rubber used is the high coefficient of thermal expansion. The coefficient of thermal expansion of a typical rubber is in the order of 10^{-3} K^{-1} . With this coefficient, a rubber expands of about 15% of its original length while heated up from room temperature to $160 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which is a typical working temperature during rubber forming. This is quite a large value which influences the final product shape, especially during series production.

Another factor that has to be taken into account is the friction that is occurring between the different components during the process. Both thermoplastic, when heated, and rubber have a large coefficient of friction and this tends to reduce the hydraulic pressure on the mould, especially in corners. This friction is considerably influenced by the dimensions of the rubber mould half. These dimensions in turn are influenced by the thermal expansion of the rubber and the evolution of the rubber temperature in the course of processing series of a product.

Pressure forming using a collection of rubber particles instead of the solid rubber mould is a newly patented method for the forming of thermoplastic composites developed at the Delft University of Technology as an improvement of the classical rubber forming of thermoplastic composites.

It presents a series of advantages which might extend the utilization to metals and other materials and increase the possible shapes and dimensions to be pressure formed. With this method [1], a collection of rubber particles is used to press the thermoplastic sheet in the metal mould in order to create the homogeneous pressure distribution that is needed during the reconsolidation phase. The method is exemplified in Figure 2. The rubber particles are held in a container connected to the press. When the thermoplastic composite has reached its matrix melting temperature and is placed between the mould and the container, the particles are pressed inside the metal mould, forming the thermoplastic into the desired shape. In this case the rubber particles act as a fluid, creating a more uniform pressure distribution [2] and thus being able to reach each corner of the mould. Yet, the numerous disadvantages of application of real fluids are

absent: there is no leaking and some spilled rubber particles can be collected and used again in the production process.

Figure 2 Schematic of the process.

In this paper the pressure distribution around a metal mould is measured with both a solid rubber stamp and a collection of particles of different shape and hardness. Comparisons are made and conclusions on the best particle's configuration are made. Finally comparisons with produced products in both methods are shown.

TEST SET UP

For both set of experiments, the test set up consists of a steel mould for press forming of U-beams. This shape is very useful as it allows carrying out tests in which the only parameter that has to be taken into account is the rubber mould, as the shearing of the fibres is not present. The results that are presented in this paper are for beams 40 mm wide and 40 mm high. The length of the mould is 180 mm.

To be able to acquire data on the pressure distribution during pressing, a test set up has been built as shown in Figure 3. In the centre of the mould a series of pressure sensor is placed. The pressure sensors are made by small metal plates 2 mm thick and 5 mm width and 10 mm length which are simply supported at each side. On the back of each metal plate a strain gauge is positioned which measures the strain due to the plate deflection. This way the pressure distribution on the three sides of the mould is measured and it is possible to have an overview of the pressure distribution around the cross section of the product during the forming and consolidation phase.

Figure 3 Metal mould and strain gauges position.

Solid mould set up

In all presented experiments, one rubber mould has been used with the same dimensions of the metal mould, where 1 mm room has been left at the sides to allow the presence of the laminate and it is shorter than the metal mould to allow the thermal expansion along its length. Actual dimensions of the rubber mould are 38 x 40 x 176 mm. The rubber is Silastic M, from Dow Corning, a silicon rubber of hardness 55 Sh A which can withstand temperatures up to 250 °C.

The laminate is a substitute of the thermoplastic laminate, where a rubber matrix replaces the softened thermoplastic matrix to simulate the viscosity and friction during the process and allow for static tests (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Rubber forming test set up

A frame around the laminate represents the so-called “blank holder”. The blank holder allows the correct positioning of the thermoplastic laminate when the laminate is heated. Moreover, the possibility to apply a tension force on the laminate and play with this force gives the possibility to see the effect of the blank holder force on the pressure distribution on the mould.

The tests have been carried out on a 25 Tons static Zwick Roell testing machine where, with the addition of an oven, it is possible to carry out tests at higher temperature.

Rubber particles set up

The container for the rubber particles is a Plexiglas box stiffened at its basis with thick aluminium reinforcement. In order to push the particles inside the mould, an aluminium piston is inserted in the Plexiglas mould as shown in Figure 5, as well as some particles used for the test.

Figure 5 Rubber particles test set up.

Two different sets of rubber particles are considered: ellipsoidal rubber particles produced by injection moulding of two different hardness and cubical rubber particles, obtained cutting a larger rubber block, of two different edge sizes and three different hardness. A summary of tested rubber shapes, dimensions and hardness can be found in

Table 1 Summary of tested particles.

Rubber Type	Hardness (Shore A)	Dimension 1 (mm)	Dimension 2 (mm)	Dimension 3 (mm)
Ellipsoid	20	7.5 x 10 x 12.5		
Ellipsoid	35	7.5 x 10 x 12.5		
Cube Zermack ZA 22 Mould	22		5 x 5 x 5	10 x 10 x 10
Cube Zermack HT 33 TRANSP	33		5 x 5 x 5	10 x 10 x 10
Cube Sylastic S	37		4 x 4 x 4	8 x 8 x 8
Cube Zermack SA 50 LT	50		5 x 5 x 5	10 x 10 x 10
Cube Sylastic M	59		4 x 4 x 4	8 x 8 x 8

DISCUSSION OF TEST RESULTS

The results are presented in excel diagrams where in the x-axis is an expanded view of the cross section of the mould where the pressure sensors are placed. In Figure 6 the position of the pressure sensors is shown, as schematised in the excel diagrams. In the y-axis the pressure distribution in the mould is shown.

Figure 6 Schematic of representation of results.

Solid mould tests

In the case of the solid rubber mould, the tests have been carried out at different temperatures from room temperature up to 150° C, which is the maximum measured temperature inside the rubber mould during production. Figure 7 shows the pressure distribution at different load steps around the mould, in the case of room temperature, 50° C, 100° C and 150° C. Unfortunately the figures are not symmetric, showing that the rubber mould was not perfectly centred during testing, which is, on the other hand, the most common case during production and therefore gives a better correspondence with reality. This is also shown by the “wrong” reading of the first (too low) and last (too high) pressure sensors which indicate a contact between the metal mould and the test set up.

Figure 7 Pressure distribution at increasing testing temperature, from RT to 150° C.

The figures show several phenomena. The average normal pressure decreases with the increase of the temperature which suggests an increase of friction on the mould walls, which decreases the normal pressure. As expected [3], up to 100° C a pressure loss in one corner of the mould is present. This pressure loss is also visible in the first readings (up to 5 kN applied load) in the case of 150° C; while for higher values the pressure at the corner reaches higher values than the average pressure. The interpretation of this result, confirmed by frequent problems during production, is that at higher temperatures, therefore after a certain amount of production cycles, when the mould is hot and at its maximum expansion, the rubber presses the laminate in the corner creating an unwanted wrinkle.

Rubber particles tests

In the case of rubber particles, whose one example of test sequence is shown in Figure 8, the results always show an almost constant pressure distribution.

Figure 8 Example of test sequence

An example of two tests carried out with the same particles is shown in Figure 9, where the pressure distribution around the mould is shown at growing values of applied load. Although there is a small variation in values, the peaks corresponding to the loss of pressure around the corners of the mould have disappeared and the higher and lower pressure values for different tests do not correspond to the same place in the mould but depends on the particle position inside the mould, as it is also visible in the last picture of the test sequence where voids in-between the particles are still visible.

Figure 9 Two examples of the pressure distribution for increasing load in the case of small 22 Sh A particles.

Figure 10 gives examples of pressure distribution at maximum applied load for the three carried out tests with particles of same dimensions and hardness. Here it is evident how the average pressure is the same, but scatter and maximum applied pressure on the mould wall are different.

Figure 10 Results for small square 22ShA, ellipsoids 22Sh A and large square 59 ShA.

A summary of all carried out tests with major results is reported in Table 2. The table evidences that for equal particle dimension, the average normal pressure on the walls of the mould is inversely proportional to the particles' hardness. This means that the harder the rubber, the higher is the increase of friction on the walls of the mould. At the same

time, the amount of scatter in the data increases with the hardness, which implies a less constant pressure distribution on the mould.

In general it is possible to conclude that the best way to obtain a constant pressure distribution is by the use of the softer rubber, if possible with the smaller particles' dimension, with a preference to ellipsoidal particles when their price is not an issue. The ellipsoid shape appears to give better results than the cubic one, but the shape seems to play a smaller role than the hardness.

Table 2 Summary of results.

	Average (MPa)	Standard Deviation (MPa)
Ellipsoids 20 Sh A	0.96	0.19
Ellipsoids 35 Sh A	0.79	0.26
Large cubes 22 Sh A	0.90	0.25
Small cubes 22 Sh A	1.01	0.20
Large cubes 33 Sh A	0.61	0.47
Small cubes 33 Sh A	0.79	0.26
Large cubes 37 Sh A	0.83	0.32
Small cubes 37 Sh A	1.08	0.26
Large cubes 50 Sh A	0.59	0.36
Small cubes 50 Sh A	0.51	0.27
Large cubes 59 Sh A	0.69	0.46
Small cubes 59 Sh A	0.95	0.37

COMPARISONS DURING PRODUCTION

To be able to verify how well the results found with the static tests apply to real products, some hemispheres have been produced with both methods. The equipment used is shown in Figure 11: the thermoplastic plate is heated between two infrared panels and then moved under the press where it is formed.

Figure 11 Equipment used for the pressure forming of the hemispheres and metal mould.

Production with solid mould

For the production of hemispheres with a solid mould, a negative rubber mould out of the metal mould shown in Figure 11 is made. The results are shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12 Rubber formed hemisphere.

The hemisphere is well formed and both external and internal surface look good although some dry spots on the external surface and a wrinkles in the internal corners are presents.

Production with rubber particles

In Figure 13 the first results [1] obtained with the rubber particles are shown. The external surface of the hemisphere is well formed and neither dry spots nor wrinkles are visible. The internal side of the mould, instead, shows clearly the imprints of the particles, in the first case large square particles 37 Sh A and in the second case ellipsoidal particles 22 Sh A, where a visible improvement is obtained in the second case. The imprint is mainly due to the resin which is squeezed in between the particles during pressing. This does not influence the quality of the product and could be even machined away after production when desired, though this would increase the amount of production time.

Figure 13 Difference of imprint of rubber particles.

Finally the results obtained with one of the first attempts of rubber pressing with soft particles 22 Sh A of the smallest dimension are presented. Although the hemisphere is not completely formed and is damaged, mainly due to the limited amount of trials with the new test set up, which still has to be tuned in applied pressure and type of blank holder, both internal and external surface look perfectly smooth and no wrinkles are present at the edge of the product. Here there is neither resin infiltration nor particle imprints visible.

Figure 14 First trial of a hemisphere produced with small square particles 22 Sh A

CONCLUSIONS

Although pressure forming of thermoplastics using rubber particles instead of a solid rubber mould is still in a developments phase, it already presents several advantages to the classical rubber pressing method. Not only is it more versatile, as a wider range of products can be formed; including pieces with undercut, but also allows the reduction of development costs related to the definition of the right rubber mould.

This paper shows that using the right combination of rubber particles shape and hardness it is possible to form a product of high quality, better than the optimised rubber pressed product. Some more work has to be carried out before this production method can be commercialised, namely the definition of the right parameters during production and the design of the optimal container for the rubber particles which can allow a fast series production.

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